

IKKINCHI VA UCHINCHI TIP KLASSIK SOHALAR DEKART KO'PAYTMALARINING BERGMAN YADROSI

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada bir jinsli doiraviy matritsaviy sohalarning Bergman yadrolari topish va ularning xossalari o'rganilgan.

***Kalit so'zlar.** Klassik sohalari, Bergman yadrosi, yakobiyani, doiraviy soha, avtomorfizm.*

ANNOTATION

This work is devoted to the search for Bergman kernels of homogeneous circular matrix domains and their properties..

***Keywords.** Classical domains, Bergman kernel, Jacobian, circular domain, automorphism.*

Ma'lumki,

$$\Phi_2 = G(B - P_2)(I^{(n)} - \bar{P}_2 B)^{-1} \bar{G}^{-1}, \quad (1.1)$$

akslantirish esa, $\mathfrak{R}_{II}(n)$ ikkinchi tip klassik sohaning, P_2 nuqtasini koordinata boshiga akslantiruvchi avtomorfizmi bo'ladi, bu yerda $Z \in \mathfrak{R}_{II}(n)$ va $G \in \mathbb{C}[n \times n]$ matritsalar quyidagi shartlarni qanoatlantiradi:

$$\bar{G}(I^{(n)} - \bar{P}_2 P_2') G' = I^{(n)}. \quad (1.2)$$

Shuningdek, quyidagi

$$\Phi_3 = A(Z - P_3)(I^{(n)} + \bar{P}Z)^{-1} \bar{A}^{-1} \quad (1.3)$$

akslantirish esa, $\mathfrak{R}_{III}(n)$ ikkinchi tip klassik sohaning, P_3 nuqtasini koordinata boshiga akslantiruvchi avtomorfizmi bo'ladi, bu yerda $Z \in \mathfrak{R}_{III}(n)$ va $A \in \mathbb{C}[n \times n]$ matritsalar quyidagi shartlarni qanoatlantiradi:

$$\overline{A}(I^{(n)} + P_3 \overline{P_3})A' = I^{(n)}. \quad (1.4)$$

Aytaylik, $\mathfrak{R}$ sohani $\mathfrak{R}_{II}(n)$ va $\mathfrak{R}_{III}(n)$ sohalarining dekart ko'paytmasi quyidagi ko'rinishida berilgan bo'lsin:

$$\mathfrak{R} = \mathfrak{R}_{II}(n) \times \mathfrak{R}_{III}(n) = \{(B, Z): B \in \mathfrak{R}_{II}(n), Z \in \mathfrak{R}_{III}(n)\},$$

bu yerda,

$$\mathfrak{R}_{II}(n) = \{B \in \mathbb{C}[n \times n]: I^{(n)} - B\overline{B} > 0, \forall B' = B\}.$$

va

$$\mathfrak{R}_{III}(n) = \{Z \in \mathbb{C}[n \times n]: I^{(n)} + Z\overline{Z} > 0, \forall Z' = -Z\}.$$

Bu $\mathfrak{R}$ sohaning $\mathfrak{X}$ ostovi, $\mathfrak{R}_{II}(n)$ va $\mathfrak{R}_{III}(n)$ sohalar $\mathfrak{X}_{II}$ va $\mathfrak{X}_{III}$ ostovlari dekart ko'paytmasiga teng bo'ladi, ya'ni

$$\mathfrak{X}_{II} = \{B \in \mathbb{C}[n \times n]: B\overline{B} = I^{(n)}, \forall B' = B\},$$

$$\mathfrak{X}_{III} = \{Z \in \mathbb{C}[n \times n]: -Z\overline{Z} = I^{(n)}, \forall Z' = -Z\}$$

$$\mathfrak{X} = \mathfrak{X}_{II} \times \mathfrak{X}_{III}.$$

U holda yuqoridagi (1.1) va (1.3) munosabatlarga asosan quyidagi tasdiq o'rinli bo'lishini topamiz:

1-tasdiq. Komponentalari mos ravishda (1.2), (1.4) shartlar bilan aniqlanadigan, (1.1) hamda (1.3) ko'rinishidagi Φ_2 va Φ_3 akslantirishlar bilan aniqlanadigan ushbu $\Phi = (\Phi_2, \Phi_3)$ akslantirish $\mathfrak{R} = \mathfrak{R}_{II}(n) \times \mathfrak{R}_{III}(n)$ sohaning

$P = (P_2, P_3) \in \mathfrak{R}$ nuqtasini koordinata boshiga akslantiruvchi avtomorfizmi bo'ladi.

Bremerman teoremasini $\mathfrak{R}_{II}(n)$ va $\mathfrak{R}_{III}(n)$ klassik sohalar dekart ko'paytmasining Bergman yadrosini topish uchun analogini keltiramiz.

1-teorema. Aytaylik, $\mathfrak{R}_{II}(n)$ va $\mathfrak{R}_{III}(n)$ sohalar $B \in \mathbb{C}[n \times n]$ va $Z \in \mathbb{C}[n \times n]$ o'zgaruvchili fazolardagi klassik sohalar va $\mathfrak{R} = \mathfrak{R}_{II}(n) \times \mathfrak{R}_{III}(n)$ bo'lsin, u holda quyidagi tenglik o'rinli bo'ladi:

$$K_{\mathfrak{R}}(B, Z, \bar{B}, \bar{Z}) = K_{\mathfrak{R}_{II}(n)}(B, \bar{B})K_{\mathfrak{R}_{III}(n)}(Z, \bar{Z}) \quad (1.5)$$

Isbot. Buning uchun 1-tasdiqqa asoslanib, $\mathfrak{R}$ sohaning $\Phi = (\Phi_2, \Phi_3)$ avtomorfizmi xususiyatlaridan foydalanamiz. Dastlab, (1.1) ko'rinishdagi Φ_2 akslantirishni differentsiallab ushbu

$$d\Phi_2 = G \left[dB \cdot (I^{(n)} - \bar{P}_2 B)^{-1} + (B - P_2) d(I^{(n)} - \bar{P}_2 B)^{-1} \right] \bar{G}^{-1},$$

tenglikka ega bo'lamiz. Agar $B = P_2$ desak u holda (1.2) shartga asosan quyidagi tenglikka ega bo'lamiz:

$$d\Phi_2 = G \cdot dB \cdot (I^{(n)} - \bar{P}_2 P_2)^{-1} \cdot \bar{G}^{-1} = G \cdot dB \cdot G'. \quad (1.6)$$

va (1.5) munosabat ushbu

$$B = \begin{pmatrix} b_{11} & b_{12} & \dots & b_{1n} \\ b_{21} & b_{22} & \dots & b_{2n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ b_{n1} & b_{n2} & \dots & b_{nn} \end{pmatrix}, G = \begin{pmatrix} g_{11} & g_{12} & \dots & g_{1n} \\ g_{21} & g_{22} & \dots & g_{2n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ g_{n1} & g_{n2} & \dots & g_{nn} \end{pmatrix}, \Phi_2 = \begin{pmatrix} h_{11} & h_{12} & \dots & h_{1n} \\ h_{21} & h_{22} & \dots & h_{2n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ h_{n1} & h_{n2} & \dots & h_{nn} \end{pmatrix}.$$

belgilashlar orqali, quyidagi tenglikka ekvivalentdir:

$$dh_{sj} = \sum_{l=1}^n \sum_{i=1}^n g_{si} db_{il} g_{lj}, s = 1, 2, \dots, n; j = 1, 2, \dots, n.$$

Bu oxirgi tenglikdan $\Phi_2 = (h_{11}, \dots, h_{nn})$ golomorf akslantirish uchun quyidagi tenglik o'rinli bo'lishi kelib chiqadi:

$$dh_{11} \wedge dh_{12} \wedge \dots \wedge dh_{nn} = \prod_{s,j} \sum_{l=1}^n \sum_{i=1}^n g_{si} db_{il} g_{lj}, s = 1, 2, \dots, n; j = 1, 2, \dots, n.$$

U holda $db_{il} = db_{li}$ ekanidan, ushbu

$$\begin{aligned} dh_{11} \wedge dh_{12} \wedge \dots \wedge dh_{nn} &= \\ &= \prod_{s,j} (\det G)^s \Psi b_{11} \Psi b_{12} \dots \Psi b_{nn} \Psi (\det G)^j, s = 1, 2, \dots, n; j = 1, 2, \dots, n. \end{aligned}$$

tenglik quyidagi

$$dh_{11} \Psi b_{12} \Psi \dots \Psi b_{nn} = (\det G)^{\frac{n+1}{2}} \Psi (\det G)^{\frac{n+1}{2}} \Psi b_{11} \Psi b_{12} \dots \Psi b_{nn} =$$

$$= J_C(\Phi_2) \cdot db_{11} \wedge db_{12} \dots \wedge db_{nn},$$

tenglikka ekvivalent bo'ladi, bu yerda $J_C(\Phi_2) - \Phi_2$ akslantirishning kompleks yakobiani va u quyidagicha topiladi:

$$J_C(F_2) = (\det G)^{\frac{(n+1)}{2}} \Psi(\det G \dot{y})^{\frac{(n+1)}{2}} = (\det G \dot{y})^{(n+1)}.$$

Bulardan (1.2) shartga asosan

$$\mathbb{F}_2^g = |J_C(F_2)|^2 \overset{g}{B} = \left| (\det G)^{n+1} \right|^2 \overset{g}{B} = \frac{\overset{g}{B}}{\det^{n+1}(I - BB)}$$

tenglikka ega bo'lamiz.

Endi (1.3) ko'rinishdagi Φ_3 akslantirishni differensiallab ushbu

$$d\Phi_3 = A \left[dZ \cdot (I^{(n)} - \bar{P}_3 Z)^{-1} + (Z - P_3) d(I^{(n)} + \bar{P}_3 Z)^{-1} \right] \bar{A}^{-1},$$

tenglikka ega bo'lamiz. Agar $Z = P_2$ desak u holda (1.4) shartga asosan quyidagi tenglikka ega bo'lamiz:

$$d\Phi_3 = A \cdot dZ \cdot (I^{(n)} + \bar{P}_3 P_3)^{-1} \cdot \bar{A}^{-1} = A \cdot dZ \cdot A'. \quad (1.6)$$

va (1.6) munosabat ushbu

$$Z = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & z_{12} & \dots & z_{1n} \\ z_{21} & 0 & \dots & z_{2n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ z_{n1} & z_{n2} & \dots & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad A = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & a_{12} & \dots & a_{1n} \\ a_{21} & 0 & \dots & a_{2n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ a_{n1} & a_{n2} & \dots & 0 \end{pmatrix},$$

$$\Phi_3 = \begin{pmatrix} v_{11} & v_{12} & \dots & v_{1n} \\ v_{21} & v_{22} & \dots & v_{2n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ v_{n1} & v_{n2} & \dots & v_{nn} \end{pmatrix}$$

belgilashlar orqali quyidagi tenglikka ekvivalentdir:

$$dv_{sj} = \sum_{l=1}^n \sum_{i=1}^n a_{si} dz_{il} a_{lj}, \quad s = 1, 2, \dots, n; \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, n.$$

Bu oxirgi tenglikdan $\Phi_3 = (v_{11}, \dots, v_{nn})$ golomorf akslantirish uchun quyidagi tenglik o'rinli bo'lishi kelib chiqadi:

$$dv_{11} \wedge dv_{12} \wedge \dots \wedge dv_{nn} = \prod_{s,j} \sum_{l=1}^n \sum_{i=1}^n a_{si} dz_{il} a_{lj}, s = 1, 2, \dots, n; j = 1, 2, \dots, n.$$

U holda $dz_{il} = -dz_{li}$ ekanidan, ushbu

$$\begin{aligned} & dv_{11} \wedge dv_{12} \wedge \dots \wedge dv_{nn} = \\ & = \sum_{s,j} (\det A)^s \Psi_{z_{11}} \Psi_{z_{12}} \dots \Psi_{z_{nn}} \Psi (\det A')^j, s = 1, 2, \dots, n; j = 1, 2, \dots, n. \end{aligned}$$

tenglik quyidagi

$$\begin{aligned} dv_{11} \Psi_{z_{11}} \Psi_{z_{12}} \dots \Psi_{z_{nn}} &= (\det A)^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \Psi (\det A')^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \Psi_{z_{11}} \Psi_{z_{12}} \dots \Psi_{z_{nn}} = \\ &= J_C(\Phi_3) \cdot dz_{11} \wedge dz_{12} \wedge \dots \wedge dz_{nn}, \end{aligned}$$

tenglikka ekvivalent bo'ladi, bu erda $J_C(F_3)$ - Φ_3 akslantirishning kompleks yakobiani va u quyidagicha topiladi:

$$J_C(F_3) = (\det A)^{\frac{(n-1)}{2}} \Psi (\det A')^{\frac{(n-1)}{2}} = (\det A')^{(n-1)}.$$

Bulardan (1.4) shartga asosan

$$F_3 = \left| J_C(F_3) \right|^2 Z = \left| (\det A)^{n-1} \right|^2 Z = \frac{Z}{\det^{n-1}(I + Z\bar{Z})}$$

tenglikka ega bo'lamiz.

Shunday qilib, yuqoridagi mulohazalarimizga ko'ra $\Phi = (h_{11}, \dots, h_{nn}, v_{11}, \dots, v_{nn})$ akslantirish uchun quyidagi

$$\begin{aligned} & dh_{11} \wedge dh_{12} \wedge \dots \wedge dh_{nn} \wedge dv_{11} \wedge dv_{12} \wedge \dots \wedge dv_{nn} = \\ & = J_C(\Phi_2) db_{11} \wedge db_{12} \wedge \dots \wedge db_{nn} J_C(\Phi_3) \wedge dz_{11} \wedge dz_{12} \wedge \dots \wedge dz_{nn} \end{aligned}$$

tenglik bajarilishi va uning haqiqiy yakobiani ushbu

$$J_R(F) = \frac{1}{\det^{n+1}(I - B\bar{B}) \det^{n-1}(I + Z\bar{Z})}$$

tenglik bilan topilishi kelib chiqadi. Ma'lumki, $\mathfrak{R}_{II}(n)$ va $\mathfrak{R}_{III}(n)$ sohalaring Bergman yadrolari quyidagi ko'rinishda topiladi:

$$K_{\mathfrak{B}_{II}(n)}(b, \bar{b}) = \frac{1}{V(\mathfrak{B}_{II}(n))} \frac{1}{\det^{n+1}(I^{(n)} - B\bar{B})},$$

$$K_{\mathfrak{B}_{III}(n)}(z, \bar{z}) = \frac{1}{V(\mathfrak{B}_{III}(n))} \frac{1}{\det^{n-1}(I^{(n)} + Z\bar{Z})},$$

bu yerda, $V(\mathfrak{R}_{II}(n))$ va $V(\mathfrak{R}_{III}(n))$ miqdorlar mos ravishda $\mathfrak{R}_{II}(n)$ va $\mathfrak{R}_{III}(n)$ sohalarning hajmlari. Demak, ushbu

$$\begin{aligned} K_{\mathfrak{B}}(B, Z, \bar{B}, \bar{Z}) &= \frac{1}{\det^{n+1}(I - B\bar{B}) \det^{n-1}(I + Z\bar{Z})} = \\ &= \frac{1}{V(\mathfrak{B}_{II}(n)) \det^{n+1}(I - B\bar{B})} \cdot \frac{1}{V(\mathfrak{B}_{III}(n)) \det^{n-1}(I + Z\bar{Z})} = \\ &= K_{\mathfrak{R}_{II}(n)}(B, \bar{B}) \cdot K_{\mathfrak{R}_{III}(n)}(Z, \bar{Z}). \end{aligned}$$

munosabatlar o'rinli bo'lishi kelib chiqadi. *Teorema isbot bo'ldi.*

Bu 1-teoremadan ushbu natija kelib chiqadi.

1-natija. Aytaylik, $\mathfrak{R}_{II}(n)$ va $\mathfrak{R}_{III}(n)$ sohalar $B \in \mathbb{C}[n \times n]$ va $Z \in \mathbb{C}[n \times n]$ o'zgaruvchili fazolardagi klassik sohalar va $\mathfrak{R} = \mathfrak{R}_{II}(n) \times \mathfrak{R}_{III}(n)$ bo'lsin, u holda quyidagi tenglik o'rinli bo'ladi:

$$K_{\mathfrak{R}}(B, Z, \bar{\Psi}, \bar{Y}) = K_{\mathfrak{R}_{II}(n)}(B, \bar{\Psi}) K_{\mathfrak{R}_{III}(n)}(Z, \bar{Y}) \quad (1.7)$$

bu yerda, $B, \Psi \in \mathfrak{R}_{II}(n)$, $Z, Y \in \mathfrak{R}_{III}(n)$.

$\mathfrak{R}$ sohada $d\mu$ o'lchov bo'yicha kvadrati bilan integrallanuvchi funksiyalar fazosini $L^2(\mathfrak{R})$ bilan, $H^2(\mathfrak{R})$ bilan esa $L^2(\mathfrak{R})$ sinfga golomorf davom qiluvchi uning qism fazoni belgilaymiz. 1-natijadan va Zommer-Mering teoremasiga asosan quyidagi teorema o'rinli bo'lishi kelib chiqadi.

2-teorema. *Ixtiyoriy $f \in H^2(\mathfrak{R})$ funksiyalar uchun*

$$f(B, Z) = \int_{\mathfrak{R}} f(\Psi, \Upsilon) K_{\mathfrak{R}}(B, Z, \bar{\Psi}, \bar{\Upsilon}) d\mu, \quad (\Psi, \Upsilon) \in \mathfrak{R}$$

Bergman-Bremermann integral formulasi o‘rinli.

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